

Mediational Role of Emotional Intelligence between Transformational Leadership and Employee's Performance

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Abstract: *The present study aims to investigate dynamic connection between transformational leadership and employee's performance (Task performance and OCB) with mediating Perception Emotional intelligence (EI) in Higher Education Institutions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The relationship between the variables of the current model is based upon different theories i.e. Vroom (1964) Expectancy Theory, LME Theory (Graen, 1976) Wang et al., (2005), as well as Social Exchange Theory proposed by (Blau,1964). Data was obtaining from public and private sector universities and through purposive sampling in dyads. Response obtain were analyze through rigorous statistical procedures i.e. CFA via AMOS in first phase, followed by bootstrapping and mediation through Preacher and Hayes (2008) SPSS macros. Findings indicate that both emotional intelligence and perception of organization politics act as a stronger role in enhancing the association between organizational citizenship behavior and transformational Leadership.*

Key Words: Transformational Leadership, OCB, Task Performance, POP, Emotional Intelligence.

Introduction

During the previous decade, higher education institution has altered its dynamics in order to foster academic excellence as well as efficiency. The changes in higher education system has created new demands for professional who performs leadership roles and the need for knowledge has also been increased how to deals with the transformed institutions ([Marshall, Adams & Cameron, 2013](#)). Bartram and Casimir (2006) evaluated that the basis of leadership model (Transformational and transactional) lies in vision and empowerment which leads to enhance employees' efficiency as well as job performance (Organizational citizenship behavior and Task performance). However, the importance of leadership model has questioned, whether the leadership model is useful (efficient) for educational sector or not ([Bartram & Casimir, 2006](#)). The foremost objective of research study is to improve the understanding and interpretation of Transformational leadership in educational sector. This research study also deals with those variables which acts as mediators in the leadership process, so that to investigate why, how and when leadership originates in educational sector. The current research study deals with mediator (Emotional Intelligence) so as to investigate the association amid leadership style and job performance attitude (Task performance and OCB) among the employees in educational sector.

Burgoyne, Mackness and Williams (2009) expressed that society has a general hope from the universities that they will create new professional to the various sectors of economy in order to foster national growth. [Bodla and Nawaz \(2011\)](#) stated that due to globalization, higher education system has made a global problem because of the shift in competition from the national levels to an international. The role of global competition in education system has increased the demands for leadership and performance ([Bodla & Nawaz, 2011](#)). [Bakar and Mahmood \(2013\)](#) interpreted that it is necessary for the higher educational institutions to enhance skills and knowledge of their employees. There must be an increase in economic resources so that to provide good economic packages for employees in order to

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boost the performance of higher educational institutions, to confirm organization success ([Bakar & Mahmood, 2013](#)). Success of any organization depend upon the visionary style of leadership and the relationship between leaders with their employees. Once the leader play its role in the true sense, result will be highly motivated work force. But in order to align the favorable conditions between employees and leaders, it is actually emotional capability of top crest to understand the situation before it turns in to disaster. There are number of studies between leaders and employees performance but the mediational effect of leader's emotional capabilities to bridge this relationship is rare. Hence the current study investigate for the first time the leader's mediational capability of controlling emotion to promote citizenship behavior among employees.

Literature Review

In the view of interpretation conducted by (Bass, 1985) expressed that transformational leaders give favorable feedback and give confidence to their subordinates to remain creative and conduct critical thinking under the difficult work situations. [Podsakoff et al. \(1990\)](#) suggested that under the effect of leadership (transformational), employees give preference to the general mission of an institution and employees will devote their energies and ensure full concentration to the organizational goals rather than focusing on the own personal interest. Employees can better understand and interpret the institutional value if employees have preferred organizational success rather than individual success. According to the research study expressed by (Bass, 1985; Yuk, 1999a, 1999b) comprised that the philosophy of transformational leadership has been generated by Burus, (1998).

The basis of transformational leadership lies in vision and empowerment and has favorable impact on worker's performance and attitude. Transformational leadership provides a main focus towards contemporaneous leadership research. The favorable impact of transformational leadership has been identified. But until researchers have obtained very little information's of how transformational leadership has emerged and has affected by the natural environment of an institution ([Bizhan, Saeid & Barghi, 2013](#)). Transformational leaders can influence follower's attitude through psychological processes and mechanism because psychological processes help to understand why transformational leadership is effective (Bakar & Mahmood, 2014). Therefore further research work is required to interpret transformational leadership in the context of higher education regarding job performance and organizational citizenship behavior.

According to Baksh, Zaman and Fida (2014) analyzed that job performance of workers can derived from individual ambitions as well as individual principles which possess unseen roots to institutional values and possess rationality for whom organization exist. Performance is multidimensional construct which contains task performance and Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) that have significant role for organizational success (Baksh, Zaman & Fida, 2014). [Fatma and Aini \(2015\)](#) interpreted that task performance represents a working process, when employees prepare task plan for the execution of a task. When employees express themselves as effective performers in their actions then task performance will be successful. Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) exhibit voluntary commitment of employees with their institutions because OCB are not mentioned in contractual task ([Fatma & Aini, 2015](#)). Performance is the outcome of those activities when workers accomplished them under diverse situation as well as diverse factors (Such as: Task performance and OCB).

Emotional Intelligence Role

On the basis of new research studies Emotional intelligence is a common indicator which transforms individuals into effective managers, innovators and leaders and shows methods to enhance the performance. EI abilities regulate, anticipate as well as utilize emotion. For example researchers have noted that the meaning of EI is to identify own feelings and others, control of emotions and empathizing with others ([Baksh, Zaman & Fida, 2015](#)). The concept of EI can be studied both in formal and informal organization. EI describes human skills of inspiration, empathy, self-control, expertise and self-awareness in association. EI guides an individual to understand human intelligence so that to quantify total intelligence of an individual employee [Irvan, Mosa & Mohmoud, 2016](#).

Transformational Leadership, Task Performance And OCB

It is very important to bring changes in organization in order to face and solve issues through diagnostic process, leadership provides good diagnostic process, leadership also provide time as well as effort to diagnose organizational issues before resolution (Bass, Avolio, Jung & Berson, 2003). Based on needs of individuals, their task as well as behavior, transformational leaders, several research processes have also interpreted the influence of transformational leadership style upon employees' performance in lieu existing research literature, interpret dominant relationship between employees' performance and transformational leadership style (Gadot & Durga, 2007). According to Abbs and Sara (2009) suggested that transformational leaders increases the motivational level of employee. So that they should be creative and understand their basic needs. Transformational leadership style enhances institutional productivity and employee's performance.

It has been confirmed that transformational leaders possess knowledge, skill as well as experience regarding the organizational activity and they don't bother to avoid risk or uncertainty (Abbas & Sara 2009). Researcher have also been conducted upon the association of transformational leadership as well as performance. Transformational leaders stimulate their subordinates to go beyond the basic operation (Shah, Nisar, Rehman, & Rehman, 2011).

The study of (Javed., 2013) indicate that transformational leadership not only enhance employees performance but it also spur the feelings of citizenship behavior among banking sector workers. Similar results were evident by (Saif., 2015) in SME's sector of Khyber PaktoonKhwa. However the major difference between (Javed., 2013 and Saif.,2015) findings is based upon the conceptual frame work of their study. Javed (2013) indicate the transformational leaders enhance employee's job performance and citizenship attributes through the mediational effect of employees collective efficacy. While Saif (2015) findings stress that transformational leaders infuse feeling of motivation in the form of OCB through organization culture and commitment. On the other side another study conducted by (Saif, Saqib, Arshad, Javed, & Khan.,2018) examine the association between leadership styles and its effectiveness through the mediational role of emotional intelligence among the banking sector employees in Islamabad. Their findings witness that transformational leaders has the highest capabilities of emotional intelligence which highlight its effectiveness as compare to that of transactional leadership.

Baker and Mahmood (2013) suggested that transformation leadership enhance job performance (Task Performance and OCB).The relation between transformation leadership and job performance is the result of (norms and condition) present in the basic agreement of employees and to whom they are subjected to perform. Research literature have expressed that transformational leadership is effective in two ways. Primarily, transformational leadership creates passion and secondly, transformational leadership causes inspirational feelings which boost up jobs satisfaction which in turn enhances performance of employees significantly (Bakar and Mahmood,2013).Fatma and Aini (2015) Analyzed that transformational leaders give motivation to workers, execute goals and objectives of the institutions. Transformational leader gives courage and motivation to attain high performance and helps to followers to solve their problems in light of new methods (Fatma and Aini,2015). Based on the previous literature (Javed., 2013 and Saif.,2015; Saif et al.,2018; Baker and Mahmood.,2013; Fatma and Aini,2015 Shah et al, 2011) following hypothesis are drawn;

Figure 1:

Based on the Above Research Model Following Hypothesis are Drawn

H₁; Transformational leadership has significantly associated with EI of employees.

H₂; Transformational leadership has “significant impact on employees” Citizenship Behavior

H₃; Transformational leadership has ‘significant impact of employees’ Task Performance.

H₄; EI and OCB are highly correlated.

H₅; EI and Task Performance are highly correlated.

H₆; EI mediate the ‘relationship between transformational” leader’s behavior and employees task performance attitude.

H₇; EI mediate the “relationship between transformational” leader’s behavior and employees Citizenship Behavior.

Methodology

Population and Sample Size

Population of the study consist of all the private and public sector HEI’s in KP. While sampling procedure was applied in two phases. In the current Study “multi stage sampling technique” was applied. In first stage the whole population (HEI’s) are dividend in 2 groups (Quota Sampling) namely (Private Sector and Government Sector).

And in the next stage through convenient sampling technique 2 Private sector and 2 public sector Universities in Capital of KP were selected. Finally, 500 faculty member and their Deans/Director/HoD and supervisory staff are selected on purposive sampling technique. The justification for the selection of 500 is based upon known population. As according to (sekran, 2000) known population chart if sample size is about 1500, than best sample size is between 350.

Constructs

Leadership

In order to measure Transformational leadership attributes adapted version of (Multi- Leadership Questionnaire) MLQ is used. Generally, MLQ developed by (Bass & Avolio., 2000) is used because of its authenticity in the research field of leadership. Response was obtained through 5 Point Likert scale.

Emotional Intelligence

Organization Citizenship Behavior.

In the current study adopted construct of [Podsakoff, Moorman, Mackenzie, and Fetter \(1990\)](#) is used to investigate the behavior of employees through leader’s response. Response was obtained through 5 point Likert scale.

Task Performance

Employee’s task performance was assessed via 7 item adapted scale of [Williams and Anderson, \(1991\)](#). Employees task related behavior was also investigated through the response of Leaders on 5 point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree and 5 represent strongly agree).

Data Analysis Procedure

In present research study use of “statistical software’s e.g. SPSS and AMOS”. As the study consist on investigating the relationship between “leadership styles and job performance through two mediators” namely POP and EI. Hence systematic procedure of data analysis are followed. CFA was performed in the first stage. In the next step Preacher and [Hayes \(2008\)](#) multi mediation statistical procedure with bootstrapping was applied.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Composition of sample from HEI’s.

Detail information about the sample characteristics obtained from different HEI’s in Khyber

Pakhtunkhwa, indicate that sample consist of 320 (84.21%) male and 60 (15.79%) female. The gender difference is because of the job nature as well as educational status of male and female in KP. The sample maximum age group belong to (26- 35 years) that comprises (55.26) percent of overall sample, followed by age group of (36-45) (26.21%), while the minimum percentage (1.31%) “belong to age group of above than 56 years”. The educational qualification of the respondent shows that most of them possess M.Phil degree (173, 45.52%) followed by (167, 43.94%) master degree holder, while 50 (13.15%) respondent that consist of having PhD Degree. In response to experience maximum number belong to those having (6-10 Year experience) which comprises (42.10%) followed by (less than 5 years) experience, while minimum ratio belong to those having higher tenure of experience i.e more than 15 year. In term of job nature 320 (84.21%) respondent have full time, permanent job in the university while (15.79%) percentage works on contract.

CFA for Transformational Leadership (IV-1)

Transformational leadership was adopted from (Padoskaf et al, 1990), which consist of six attributes that determine the behavior of (Trnsf) leadership in Pakistani HEI's. Result of fit indices about 5 factor (transfer) leadership are appropriate. The values of ($\chi^2/df=2.33$), (CFI= .90) and (RMSEA=.0152) see table (1). In earlier studies the same five factor model of Leadership to determine the nature of transformational behavior was used by (Saif et al, 2016) in Pakistan SME's sector, while (Javid and LeCaz, 2011) in Banking sector of Pakistan. As the loading of the all the items on their relevant factor are higher than (0.50). Hence it can be used for further analysis. (See Appendix-2).

Table 1. Fit Indices of 5 Factor Model of Leadership (Transformational).

Factor	χ^2/df	GFI	NFI	CFI	AGFI	RMESA
Transformational Leadership	2.33	.942	.897	.903	.906	.0152

Figure 2: CFA for Transformational leadership in HEI's

Assumption for CFA (Convergent and Discriminate Validity).

In order to understand the variation in (Transfer) leadership 5 factor model. Statistical procedure approved by (Formal & Lorcker.,1981) and used by [Javed and LeCaz, \(2011\)](#); Saif et al, (2015). In the recommendation of statistical procedure by [Fornell and Larcker \(1981\)](#) as well as Podsakof et al (2005) we also investigate the discriminate and convergent values of validity for transformational leadership. PVC valves actually explain the value of proper proportion of different item under one or more factor.

In the next step we measured shared variances among various factors of (Trnsf) leadership from table it is clearly evident that there is no higher correlation among variance factors while reliability of construct was measured by Joreskog Rho values. The reliability values are within the prescribed range i.e. above than 0.70. Joreskog Rho value for IM is (0.81), IC(0.73), IVS(0.77) IF (0.82) and IS (0.74). As there is no high correlation between factors of transformational Leadership (see table 2). So the construct can be used for further analysis.

Table 2. Convergent and Discriminate validity for Transformational (Trnsf) Leadership.

	IS	IC	IIB	IM	IIA	Construct Reliability (CR)
IS	0.53					.81
IC	0.53	0.40				.73
IIB	0.38	0.34	0.47			.78
IM	0.57	0.54	0.31	0.51		.82
IIA	0.14	0.16	0.08	0.26	0.42	.74

CFA for combine effect of both (DV's) (OCB and Task Performance)

In order to measure combine effect of both variables multidimensional CFA was run Factor loading results show that two item from task performance and on item from three factors of OCB was removed because of poor loading. The model fit result show that overall value of fit indices are in acceptable range. (4.6).

Table 3. Fit Indices of 5 Factor Model of OCB and Task

Factor	χ^2/df	GFI	NFI	CFI	AGFI	RMSEA
OCB & Task	1.63	.880	.922	.910	.812	.0623

Figure 3: CFA for Employees OCB and Task in HEI's.

Measurement of Validity for Combine Effect of (OCB & Task Performance) Discriminate and Convergent.

In order to understand the variation in OCB 5 factor model. Statistical procedure approved by (Formal & Lorcker.,1981) and used by [Javed and LeCaz, \(2011\)](#); Saif et al, (2015). In the recommendation of statistical procedure by [Fornell and Larcker \(1981\)](#) as well as Podsakof et al (2005) we also investigate the discriminate and convergent values of validity for OCB and Task Performance. After calculating PVC indices for all the five factors of OCB. In the next stage we calculate shared variances of all the factors. For measurement of convergent validity, PVC indices were entered, that actually explain the nature of variance of various items in relevant factors. The value of PVC Indices are as following for six factor model of OCB and Task Performance is as following.

- PVC index for factor one of OCB (Altruism-ALTR) is 0.53
- PVC index for factor Two of OCB (Conscientious - CONS) is 0.42
- PVC index for factor Three of OCB (Sportsmanship -SPMS) is 0.43
- PVC index for factor Four of OCB (Courtesy-COUR) is 0.51
- PVC index for factor Five of OCB (Civic Virtue-CVR) is 0.42

PVC indices for task performance (TaskP) is 0.44.

For the measurement of convergent as well as discriminate validity we focus on the value of task performance and its correlation with other factors of OCB. Table (4.5) indicate that PVC indices of Task performance is higher than its correlation with OCB factor's.

Table 4. Convergent and Discriminate validity for OCB and Task.

	ALTR	CONS	SPMS	COUR	CVR	Task. P	Construct reliability
ALTR	0.53						0.81
CONS	0.22	0.52					0.76
SPMS	0.23	0.17	0.43				0.80
COUR	0.30	0.44	0.31	0.51			0.81
CVR	0.21	0.19	0.11	0.31	0.42		0.79
TaskP	0.33	0.29	0.22	0.17	0.30	0.44	0.83

Regression Result for Direct and Mediating Effect via Preacher and Hayes.

From table (4.6) results about the direct path effect of IV over DV and mediating variable (EI) effect on dependent variable (Task Performance) are presented. Results “indicate that the relationship between transformational leadership” and Task Performance (DV1) is significant. Values of Path coefficient are (Coeff=.18, p<.05). Hence our hypothesis number three (H3) is accepted. These are in line with (Javed & LeCaz,2011; Saif et al,2014, ,Chan and Chan,2005). Saif et al (2014) investigate the detail relationship “between transformational leadership and employees OCB” among Pakistani Banking sector. Similarly Javed and LeCaz (2011) investigate the “relationship between leadership”, job performance with employees self and collective efficacy as mediators.

While the current study focus on investigating the relationship between these variables in HEIs of Pakistan. The relation between transformational leadership and EI is also proved via path a1 (Coeff=.22; p=.05).Which leads toward the acceptance of H1.Similar results were found by (.....).

Table 5. Results of Model-1 Direct Hypothesis (IV1, MV1, MV2,DV1)

		Coeff:	P	H.S	Results
Path c (IV1----DV2)	Direct Path (TRNSF----TPR)	.18	.00	H3	Accept
Path a (IV1---MV-1)	IV1(TRNSF)--- MV1 (EI) a1	.22	.05	H1	Accept
Path b(MV1,2---DV2)	MV1(EI)----- DV (TPR) b1	.29	.01	H4	Accept

IV= Independent Variable; MV; Mediating Variable, DV= Dependent Variable; TRP= Task Performance, EI= Emotional intelligence, TRNSF= Transformational Leadership.

From table (4.7) it is clearly indicated that at the level of ninety five percent (95%) confidence interval o does not exist for both mediator's Emotional intelligence. Results reveal that both emotional intelligence act as a stronger role in enhancing the relationship between Transformational Leadership and task performance (DV-2) .Hence it is concluded that both the mediating hypothesis H6 is accepted.

Table 6. Results for Mediating Hypothesis.

Task Performance (TPR) (DV2)	Point of Estimate	Hypothesis Results	Sample Size (n=380)	
			Lower	Upper
Total Indirect Effect	.13		.06	.20
Indirect effect--- (EI) (MV1)	.05	Accept H6	.02	.11

Results indicate that the relationship between transformational leadership (Independent variable 2) and OCB (DV-2) is significant. Values of Path coefficient are (Coeff=.22, p<.05). Hence our hypothesis number three (**H2**) is accepted. These are in line with (Javed & LeCaz,2011; Saif et al,2014, Saif et al,2016,Chan and Chan,2005). Saif et al (2016) investigate the detail relationship between different factors of transformational leadership and employees OCB among Pakistani SME's sector. While the current study focus on investigating the relationship between these variables in HEIs of Pakistan. The relationship between transformational leadership, EI (MV) is also significant, which is already proved in current Model. Results for direct relationship between Transformational Leadership (IV) to employees Citizenship behavior (DV) through path (c) is (Coeff=.44; p<.05), IV2 to MV1 through path (a1) is (Coeff=.22; p=.05), IV2 to MV2 through path (a2) is (Coeff= -.31; p<.00), MV1 to DV2 through path (b1) is (Coeff=.27; p<.05), MV2 to DV2 through path (b2) is (Coeff=.20; p<.05).

Table 7. Results of Model 4 Direct Hypothesis (IV2, MV1, MV2,DV2)

		Coeff:	P	H.S	Results
Path c (IV----DV2)	Direct Path (TRNSF-----OCB)	.44	.00	H₂	Accept
Path a (IV---MV)	IV1(TRNSF)--- MV1 (EI) a1	.22	.05	H₇	Accept
	MV1(EI)----- DV (OCB) b1	.27	.01	H₄	Accept
Path b (MV1 ---DV2)	`IV= Independent Variable; MV ; Mediating Variable, DV = Dependent Variable; OCB = Organization Citizenship Behavior, EI = Emotional intelligence, TRNSF = Transformational Leadership.				

From table (4.9) it is clearly indicated that at the level of ninety five percent (95%) confidence interval does not exist for mediator Emotional intelligence (MV1). Results reveal that emotional intelligence act as a stronger role in enhancing the relationship between Transformational Leadership (IV2) and OCB (DV2) .Hence it is concluded that both the mediating hypothesis **H₇** is accepted.

Table 8. Results for mediating hypothesis Model-2.

Organization Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (DV2)	Sample Size (n=380)			
	Point of Estimate	Hypothesis Results	BCA 95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
Total Indirect Effect	.22		.16	.41
Indirect effect--- (EI) (MV1)	.13	Accept H₇	.09	.19

Conclusion

From the results it is proved that Transformational leadership shows positive relationship with employees in role (Task) performance. Results of the current study are in line with (Vigoda,2007; Javed and LeCaz,2011; Eran,2007;Ling et al, 2011), they report positive relationship between transformational leadership and in role performance. Javed and LeCaz, (2011) study was conducted in Banking sector of Pakistan. In the current study transactional leadership shows stronger relationship with task performance as compare to transformational leadership. Few of the studies (Vigoda,2007; Eran,2007) indicate that transformational leadership is the stronger predictor of Task performance, while (Javed and LeCaz,2011) findings lead to favor transactional leadership in comparison to transformational, and (Ling et al, 2011) results favor both the style of leadership in the presence of employees feeling of job satisfaction. One of the reason that support the findings of the current study may the variation in cultural norms as well as job status. In Higher Education Institutions (HEI's) of Pakistan rules and regulation for job performance is in accordance to the guideline issued by Higher Education Commission (HEC) Pakistan. All these rules are to be followed in true spirit, and any deviances from the rules can lead toward termination of the employment. At the same time HEC provide financial support to its stake holders for extra ordinary achievement in their relevant field. More specifically if employees (Faculty Members) are performing their job on Tenure Track System (TTS) or Interim Placement, in such case role of financial benefit encourage employees to produce at the higher level.

From the result of the current study it can be deduced that transformational leaders infuse feeling of motivation among the employees, they consider each employees individually and try to enhance employee's performance in group goals attainment. Hence by motivating individual and giving them confidence that they (employees) are the stronger asset of organization, employees not only complete their assigned tasks (task performance) but also help colleagues and peers (OC Behavior) to finalizing their work. In the case of Pakistani HEIs transformational leadership is mostly found in Government sector universities. These universities employees try to complete their own assigned task and help peers to complete their task without any financial rewards. The relationship between employees build upon social fabric, which motivate them to help their colleagues. It is in line Social Exchange Theory, that focuses on the inter relationship between individuals based upon the social values, ethos, and norms.

On the other hand, Transformational leadership is also found positive association with emotional intelligence and cause (22%) variation as compare to transactional leadership (41%) variation. Generally, the findings of the current study are in line with (Mir & Abbasi ,2012; Saif et al, 2017; [Nath, 2013](#); Pillay, Vivers and Mayer, 2013; Barbuto & Burbach, 2006; Sayeed & Shanker. 2009; Khan et al, 2014). Leaders with high level of emotional intelligence infuse feeling of motivation among employees. They also help the employees in achieving the organization vision, and prepare them to tackle the organization and technological changes effectively. Transformational leaders have changed its role from simple leader Member Exchange to inspirational and motivational leader. It is basically the emotional intelligence capabilities of the leaders that mold the behavior of its employees. Technically if employees are inspired from their leaders, they will portray both in role and OC behavior.

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